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Editorial

The first 2025 issue of **Revista Letras Raras (RLR)**, the academic journal of the Laboratory for Studies in Literature and Languages in Contemporary Times at the Federal University of Campina Grande (LELLC–UFCG), is the first to be organized in a continuous publication model. Throughout the year, scientific dissemination texts were released, culminating in the publication of this editorial and its introduction at the end of the 2025 calendar year.

In its 14th volume, the journal presents the dossier **Languages, Literatures, and Contemporaneity**, maintaining an ongoing partnership with Prof. Dr. Alain-Philippe Durand from the University of Arizona (UA), as well as with **RLR**'s editors, Prof. Dr. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG) and Prof. Dr. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva from the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB). Whenever possible, we bring together works by researchers from Brazil and abroad, who collectively contribute to broadening and diversifying contemporary debates on linguistic practices, literary phenomena, representations, discourses, and processes of meaning-making across multiple forms of language.

The articles in this issue address topics in linguistics, multimodal textual genres, phonetics, sociolinguistics, language teaching, and literary analysis. They are the result of work developed by professors, students, and other researchers affiliated with institutions from various regions of Brazil, such as the Federal University of Santa Maria (UFSM), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), State University of Maringá (UEM), Federal University of Technology – Paraná (UTFPR), Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), State University of Bahia (UNEB), Federal University of Amapá (UNIFAP), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Rondônia (UNIR), University of Southern Santa Catarina (UNISUL), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), State University of Londrina (UEL), Federal Center for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca (CEFET-RJ), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), Federal University of Tocantins

(UFT), Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul (PUCRS), Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), State University of Piauí (UESPI), Federal University of Pará (UFPA), Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), São Paulo State University (UNESP), Federal University of Ceará (UFC), State University of Goiás (UEG), La Salle University (UNILASALLE), University of São Paulo (USP), Paulista University (UNIP), University of Passo Fundo (UPF), Feevale University, and the University of Bologna (UNIBO), among other Brazilian institutions that enrich the epistemological and methodological plurality represented in this volume.

We also highlight the participation of authors affiliated with international institutions, especially our ongoing partnership with the University of Arizona (USA), which reinforces the international and collaborative character of this academic journal.

To read all the texts gathered in this issue, readers may scan the QR code available on the journal's social media and directly access the articles, the review, the essay, and the artistic productions published in this dossier. We also invite you to share these works with colleagues, research groups, and students, thus contributing to the circulation of knowledge and the strengthening of academic dialogue.

Confident in this sharing, dear reader, we wish you an excellent reading experience.

Prof^a. Dr^a. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFCG, Brasil)
Prof^a. Dr^a. Maria Rennally S. da Silva (UFPB, Brasil)

Editors of *Letras Raras Journal* - Academic Journal of the LELLC Research Group /
Laboratory of Contemporary Language and Literature Studies / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Beatriz Soares